

PRIMARY PROCESSING TECHNOLOGY OF SILK WASTE FOR USE IN SIMILAR INDUSTRIES

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ABSTRACT

Research has shown that in recent years the cocoon industry, technological processes from cocoon cultivation to production of silk products and the equipment used in these processes are improving. However, due to the fact that the quality of the cocoons grown in our republic does not correspond to such techniques and technologies, the output of silk fiber waste is still high, and it continues to be exported as raw materials without processing. Although the price of 1 kg of raw silk is 48-50 US dollars in the world market, depending on its assortment, the price of silk spun from its fiber waste is 70 US dollars. In the article, the issue of preliminary processing and effective use of fiber waste of coir raw materials is widely covered.

The purpose. Currently, textile products are produced, sold and used for public consumption in many parts of the world. Based on the classification of natural silk fiber waste, it consists of preparing raw materials for the production of high-quality spun silk bobbin yarn by means of preliminary processing using surface-active substances and electroactive water, as well as the equipment that implements it.

Methods. By reducing the two times of preliminary processing implemented in accordance with the traditional technology of preliminary processing of silk waste, bringing it to one time; saving labor, energy and other resources during preliminary processing; improving the quality of deglutized and degreased fiber; increasing the amount of yarn; reduce the effect of soap and boiling water dissolved in calcium soda, which have a negative effect on silk fibers; instead, using surfactants synthesized from silk fiber wastes that are not used in production, and finally, using automatic machines used in chemical cleaning of clothes, to ensure the aesthetics of production, and to determine the alternative values of the pretreatment technology of this machine to silk fiber wastes.

Results. As a result of the study, the waste cut from the cocoons of cocoons is a relatively uniform cocoon in terms of fiber length, which is steamed and wraps the cocoons on the surface of the cocoons before they are sent to the supplier and cut at the end of each work shift according to their technological dimensions. it was determined that the length depends

on the diameter of the installed cocoon and the thickness of the cocoon threads wrapped on the surface of the cocoon.

Summary. By analyzing the literature on the preliminary processing of silk fiber waste and the scientific research works conducted in our republic and foreign countries in this direction, experiments on the use of silk fiber waste in similar industrial enterprises were studied.

INTRODUCTION

In the world market, the demand for silk fiber is increasing year by year. According to the data of "International Consultative Committee on Raw Silk (ISAC)", in recent years, 153 thousand tons of silk fiber have been produced worldwide. More than cocoon raw materials were prepared [1]. Effective use of coir raw materials on a global scale, more involvement in the production of its fiber waste as secondary raw materials, improvement of product quality and expansion of assortment types, cost reduction, identification of factors that negatively affect product quality at all stages of preliminary processing and processing of fiber waste and their elimination special attention is paid to In this regard, it is important to increase the competitiveness of silk products in the world market in order to further improve the consumer properties of silk fiber.

Uzbekistan ranks fourth in the world in the production of silk fiber, after China, India and Vietnam, and produces 26 thousand tons of cocoons [2;35 42-p]. When this indicator is compared, on average, 48-50 kg of cocoons of different sizes are obtained from 1 box of silkworm seeds. Of these produced cocoons, 68.3% belong to varieties I and II, 3.04% to non-standard, 16.12% to non-variable and 12.03% to unfit cocoons. In countries with a developed silk industry, 58.1 64.6 kg of cocoons are obtained from 1 box of silkworm seeds. 79.2 79.4% of the obtained cocoons are medium-sized cocoons and 92.1 95.19% correspond to type I [3;755 757-p], [4;334 338-p].

In this regard, special attention is being paid to improving the properties of silk threads, effective use of silk waste, further increasing the consumer properties of silk products, and developing technologies for making high-strength silk threads.

In our republic, 3-3.2 kg of dry sorted cocoons are still used to produce 1 kg of raw silk. However, in China and India, this indicator does not exceed 2.8 kg [5;4-p], [6;47 50-p]. As a result of this, more than 1 kg of various types of waste, including more than 0.6 kg of 9 different types of fibrous waste, are generated in the process of production of 1 kg of raw silk in the spinning enterprises [7;18 19-p]. A great economic benefit is obtained as a result of the full use of this waste, its processing and the production of textile products necessary for industrial and population needs [8;13 17-p].

In our republic, complex measures are being implemented to increase the competitiveness of a wide range of high-quality and low-cost textile and light industrial products based on the production and deep processing of silk fiber, which is the main textile raw material.

In the implementation of these tasks, the productivity of each box of silkworm seeds grown by cocoon-growing organizations should be increased to 65-70 kg, the silkiness of living cocoon shells should be 51-53%, the technological properties of cocoons and cocoons

should be preserved during the initial processing processes, the total amount of raw materials should be the first and second grade cocoons need to reach at least 90-95%.

It is known that in the following years, our republic took the fourth place in the world in terms of cocoon cultivation after China (650,000 t), India (280,000 t) and Vietnam (50,000 t), producing 26,000 t per year. is growing more cocoons than [2;35 42-p].

Silkworm feeding and the production of high-quality cocoons depend mainly on mulberry leaves, which are silkworm food [15; 355, 359-p]. Therefore, 50,193.3 g of mulberry orchards were established in our Republic in order to ensure the production of high-quality, abundant cocoons, and there are 80,733,800 mulberry seedlings in these orchards (see the Table 1).

Table1

The amount of prepared live cocoons and cocoon available areas in cocooning season of 2017 in our republic

№	Areas	Available mulberry orchards		Amount of live cocoons produced, b
		Mulberry orchards, acre	single row mulberries, a thousand	
1	Republic of Karakalpakstan	2541,0	3283,2	852,6
2	Andijan	4683,1	5397,6	3303,4
3	Bukhara	5222	13582	3099,71
4	Jizzakh	2192	2350	641,5
5	Kashkadarya	7303,1	3923,5	3082,1
6	Navoi	1444,5	2783	1007,9
7	Namangan	3048,2	6177,7	2727,2
8	Samarkand	8262	10413,5	2829,75
9	Surkhandarya	3434,2	7617,4	1552,7
10	Syr Darya	1551,5	1591,1	616,0
11	Tashkent	3053,7	5719,9	1641,44
12	Fergana	3297	13354,4	2714,94
13	Khorezm	4158	4540,5	2178,36
Total		50193,3	80733,8	26347,6

Currently, there are 28 cocooning enterprises in our republic for full processing of 26347.6 tons of wet cocoons grown in our republic, and a total of 2139 tons are produced in these cocooning enterprises. mainly 2.33 and 3.23 tex linear density raw silk is produced.

There are mainly Chinese (FEIYU-2000 EX, FY-2000 EX, FY-2008 and KMS), South Korea (KSS-RS-100, KMS), Japan (NISSAN) and Uzbekistan (KSM 10, KS 10). equipped with 80 series of automatic cocoons and 10 series of mechanical cocoons, the total number of hangers is 32550.

In general, the production of silk yarn from recycled silk fiber waste is one of the productive activities in the silk industry. In particular, compared to the price of 1 kg of raw silk in the world market, the price of silk kalava yarn spun from its fibrous waste is 1.5-1.6

times higher. That is why silk fiber spinning enterprises are among the most efficient enterprises of the silk industry. Therefore, it is of scientific and practical importance to constantly improve the technologies of processing silk fiber waste and to conduct comprehensive scientific research on the production of silk bobbin yarn spun from it.

METHODS.

Based on the above considerations, the article consists of theoretical and practical studies, carried out on the basis of scientific laboratories and production enterprises. Research work was carried out in two stages in order to achieve the research implementation plan and the goals and objectives set forward.

In the first stage of the research, reducing the two-fold preliminary processing, which was put into practice in accordance with the traditional technology of preliminary processing of silk waste, and bringing it to one time; saving labor, energy and other resources during preliminary processing; improving the quality of deglutized and degreased fiber, increasing the amount of tarandi obtained; reduce the effect of soap and boiling water dissolved in calcium soda, which have a negative effect on silk fibers; instead, using surfactants synthesized from silk fiber wastes that are not used in production, and finally, using automatic machines used in chemical cleaning of clothes, to ensure the aesthetics of production, and to determine the alternative values of the pretreatment technology of this machine to silk fiber wastes.

After determining the feasibility of using the machine used in chemical cleaning of clothes, its effect on the amount of residual sericin, oil, waxy fatty substances in silk and on the increase of thread production was studied.

In the initial stages of the research, automatic household LG-6 and LG-8 washing machines, Zaychenko equipment (saxlet apparatus) for determining the amount of residual sericin, fat and waxy fat in raw materials were used [9; 55; p. 56].

In order to determine the rapid realization of the technology of preliminary processing of silk waste and to determine the residual sericin, oil and waxy fatty substances, technological regimes were chosen voluntarily, the life of the loom, the amount of detergents, and the temperature of the solvent were taken into account.

In the second stage, the recommended preliminary working technology was tested in the production workshops of "Harir Tola" LLC in Andijan region, and its specific efficiency was studied.

All practical studies were carried out on group 2 raw materials - 50% of cocoon slime group and 50% of other types of silkworm waste were used. Also, the 1st grass from the cocoon was tested with preliminary treatment. Only the 1st pass was treated 100% individually.

The high-temperature technological water used in the process of preparing the cocoon for spinning, finding the end of the silk thread and spinning, and the fatty substances melted from the sponge during these processes are absorbed into the fibrous waste of silk. Also, sericin, an adhesive substance in silk fiber, is separated in the above processes, process water is added to the used chemicals and absorbed into fiber waste, forming residual oil, residual sericin, residual soap and waxy substance - waxes [10; 86 89 p].

As silk waste is produced, when dried as it is, it resembles a coarse hemp-like fiber. Therefore, they are pre-treated and the residual sericin, oil, waxy substance and soap content are processed in spinning mills and spun silk bobbin yarn is obtained.

These substances in silk waste have different solubilities and are extracted from silk waste using different solvents. Dichloroethane, methyl alcohol, gasoline and carbon (IV) chloride are often used as solvents.

There are several methods for determining the amount of residual sericin, oil, and soap in silk waste, of which the extraction method using Zaychenko equipment is the simplest and most common method (Fig. 2.1). The Zaychenko equipment is also known as the saxlet apparatus in production enterprises and it consists of the following: a conical flask (1), a return cooler (2), a glass sleeve (3), a glass cartridge (4), 4-5 g of silk fiber waste on an analytical scale 1 It is weighed with an accuracy of 0.0 mg and placed in a glass sleeve. There is a hole under the glass sleeve into which filter paper is placed [11;9-11-p].

Figure 1. Zaychenko equipment (Saxlet equipment)

The fiber waste sample is covered with the same filter paper. The glass sleeve is connected to the tube of the return cooler by means of a thread. The condenser and the glass sleeve are connected by a conical flask of definite mass, and one of the organic solvents, such as dichloroethane, methyl alcohol, benzene, or carbon (IV) chloride, is poured through the top hole of the condenser. The distance between the solvent and the sleeve should be 1 cm. The flask is placed in an electric sand bath. When the solvent begins to boil, its vapors go to the cooler, condense and drip into the sleeve.

Drops of the solvent pass through the samples of silk waste and fall into the flask, extracting the fatty substances. The extraction time is 45-50 minutes. The extraction process is considered complete if no oil remains on the filter paper.

Continuing to heat the flask, the sleeve is replaced with a glass cartridge and the solvent is expelled. The solvent collected in the cartridge is collected in another container and this solvent can be reused.

After removing the solvent, the flask is dried in a drying cabinet at a temperature of 100-1050 C for 60 minutes, cooled to room temperature, and its weight is weighed, and the

amount of residual sericin, oil and waxy oil is determined in percent using the following equations

$$X = (a \cdot 100) / H \quad (1)$$

here **a** is oil, sericin or waxy oil residue, g

N - silk waste weight, g.

The technological properties of silk fiber waste are evaluated by its weight, the content of other types of objects, sponge residue, defective cocoons added to the cocoon sludge without being spun, etc. [54; 55].

3 samples of 100 g are taken from the batch of waste prepared to be sent to the spinning enterprise to determine the amount of other types of items in the fiber waste of silk, the moisture content of the waste, the amount of cotton residue. After storing the obtained samples in a standard environment (at $220 \text{ C} \pm 20 \text{ C}$, $W 65 \% \pm 3\%$) for 24 hours, they are weighed on a technical balance with an accuracy of 0.01 g, and the weight of each sample is weighed separately, including other items in it, residual cones. was calculated by the following equation

$$g = (G_1 / G) \cdot 100 \quad (2)$$

here G is the weight of the silk waste sample, grams;

G₁ - weight of other items in silk waste;

g₁ is the amount of other items in the sample, %.

The amount of cocoon slime produced during the preparation for cocooning is determined as follows. The cocoon slime formed during the cocooning process is collected and dried at 900 C in the form of bundles of 350-450 g. The dried cocoon slime is kept in a standard temperature room for 24 hours and weighed on a technical balance to the nearest 1.0 g. Then it is calculated by the following expression

$$B_{cd} = 100 \cdot M_{cd} / M_k \quad (3)$$

here M_{sd} is the weight of cocoons, grams;

M_k is the weight of the cocoon, in grams;

V_{sd} is the amount of cocoon slime in the sample, %.

According to the standard used by enterprises, the output of cocoon sludge must not exceed 1.0%.

Determination of cocoon shell, unsucked cocoon and silkiness of the boll is carried out as follows. During the whole shift, the cocoons are harvested separately. Mixing the collected wells thoroughly, the collected total amount is sampled in the amount of 500 g from different places of the well. All the collected unwashed cocoons and 500 g samples are dried at a temperature of no more than 900 C. Then it is kept in a standard medium for 24 hours and weighed on a technical scale with an accuracy of 0.1 g. Weighed samples are cut and cleaned of fungus and worm shells. Shells of boiled and unwashed cocoons are re-weighed separately on the previously weighed scale with an accuracy of 0.1 g. According to the results of the sample, the average weight of one drill is determined, the output of the drill is calculated using the following expression

$$B_{ob.k.} = 100 \cdot M_{ob.k.} / M_k \quad (4)$$

in which $M_{ob.n.}$ - weight of unwashed cocoons, grams;

M_k is the total weight of the unwashed cocoon, grams.

The weight of unpeeled cocoons must not exceed 1%. The same is the case with the extraction of the shell of the well. Only $M_{ob.n.}$ to the expression (1.5). instead of the weight of the drill shell, and instead of M_k , the total weight of the sampled 500 g drill is put. It is worth noting that the amount of shelling of the well should not exceed 7%. Also, the silkiness of the silk is calculated by the following expression through the results of a 500 g sample

$$III_{od} = 100 \cdot M_{od.} / M_o \quad (5)$$

in which $M_{od.}$ - weight of the boiler shell, gr;

M_o - the total weight of the drill, gr.

The silkiness index of the boiler must not exceed 16%. Rings of silk produced during cocooning appear when the cocoon thread is broken or a defect in the silk is removed. Such silk waste is kept in a standard environment for 24 hours, then weighed to the nearest 0.01 g and calculated using the following expression

$$B_r = 100 \cdot M_r / M_k \quad (6)$$

here M_r is the weight of raw silk rings, gr;

M_k - the weight of the cocoon placed in the cocoon, gr.

The output of silk rings should not exceed 0.5%.

RESULTS

Fiber waste of natural silk is divided into two classes depending on the origin - cocoon industry and silk industry waste [12;8-9 p].

Wastes from the cocoon industry include fluffy cocoon sludge and unusable cocoons, black cocoons produced during cocoon cultivation and initial processing. Fluffy cocoon slime is formed in the process of collecting cultivated cocoons and makes up about 3.2-3.5% of the total amount of cocoons.

The amount of invalid cocoons is 15% of the total amount of cultivated cocoons. The fluffy slime of the cocoon is formed on the uppermost surface of its shell, and serves as a support for the silkworm when wrapping the cocoon. Such slimes are formed during the process of collecting cocoons when they are removed from the bundles and in the slime collecting machine in the cocoon sorting shop of the cocooning enterprise. Among the silk waste, these los are a raw material of little value. It contains up to 40% fiber with uneven linear density (340-350 mg/tex), and sericin content is 45-50%. The length of fibers in cocoon slime is 25-140 mm, and it is more contaminated with remains of plants - mulberry leaves and cocoon stalks [13;64 67 p].

Unusable cocoons are cocoons that cannot be completely or partially spun, 9 types of cocoon fiber waste of natural silk, including double (1.0-2.0%), ugly (distorted) (0.2-0.4%), smooth (satin) shell (1.5-3.0 %), spotted (1.0-2.0 %), black (0.5-1.0 %), unwrapped (0.5-1, 0 %), thin shell (0.3-0.6 %), hollow cocoons (0.1-0.2 %), and other defective spun silk (0.9-1.8 %) wastes (See Figure 3.2).

Fig. 2. In the general batch of unsorted cocoons relative amount of defective cocoons

Professor E. N. Mikhaylov, A. A. Sukhanov and other researchers studied the causes of the formation of defective cocoons and were summarized and concluded by Professor E. B. Rubinov [14;368 369- p], They said that the above-mentioned defective in cocoons, except for double cocoons, the amount of silk is 25-40%. Silkiness of double cocoons (cocoons with two or more silkworms wrapped together) is 45-67%.

There is also silk waste in silkworm seed factories, and the cocoon becomes a butterfly and pierces the shell of the seed cocoons. This type of silk waste is the most expensive raw material for the production of spun silk. However, its value may decrease in some cases, because seed pods are mixed with non-seed pods. Inside the mixed cocoons is a dead worm or fungus, its amount is 17% of the weight of the cocoons. The amount of silk in cocoons from which worm seeds are grown reaches 83-85%.

Unfit cocoons that are removed by cocoons during picking from the bunch and cocoons that are removed during preliminary cocoon processing (killing and drying of the cocoons) are called defective cocoons. The total amount of this type of cocoons is 16-17% of prepared wet cocoons.

The cocoons that are separated in the sorting workshop of the cocooning enterprise and are not suitable for cocooning are called cocoons with silk cocoons, compared to the quality of cocoons with defects in cocoon preparation, the quality is lower than cocoons with silk cocoons, this type of cocoons mainly includes black cocoons.

Fiber waste generated in the cocooning plant is divided into cocoon sorting plant waste, cocoon spinning plant waste, and product quality control and packaging department waste.

The cocoon sorting plant waste includes fluffy cocoon sludge - that is, the waste generated in the cocoon mixing unit, shell surface cocoon collection and cocoon sizing unit. Also, the defective cocoons collected during the sorting of the cocoons by their appearance are also classified as waste from the sorting shop.

The wastes of the cocooning workshop include cocoon slime, rope-like cocoon slime, silk rings, cocoon, non-fusible cocoons, silk clippings wrapped in yarns, etc. [15;67 69 p].

Table 2 provides information on silk wastes, types and equipment used in spinning mills.

Table2

Fiber waste cocooning equipment output amount (%)

Names of fiber waste	Equipment type and system		
	AutomaticCK-5	FEIYU 2000 EX	Mechanics KMC-10
String-shaped cocoon slime	5-7	7-9	3-4
Silk knots	3-3,5	--	--
Cocoon long line	0,8-0,9	0,9-1,0	0,9-1,0
boiler	7,8	7,8	6-7
Non-degradable cocoons	0,7-0,8	0,7-0,8	0,8-0,9
Silk cuttings in juvas	8,0-1,0	0,8-1,0	--
Bellows drill	29,82	28,49	32,40

The authors of the researches [16;210-p], [17;29 32-p] concluded that the processing of fibers with a length of 280 mm and stapled by cutting cannot ensure a positive change in the technical and economic indicators of the enterprise. Perhaps the main reason for reaching such a conclusion is that the fibers on the surface of the cocoon were hand-tipped.

In the practice of enterprises, it has been found that the brush mechanism in the steamed cocoon shaking machine searches for a continuous end of the cocoon thread on the surface of the steamed cocoon shell during its reciprocating movement, and the found end of the cocoon thread is fed to the hook of the cocoon shaking mechanism. The cocoons that have found the end of the thread stand for $t = 3 - 4$ minutes until they are fed to the spinning machine. The movement speed of the shaker is $V = 4.8 - 5.0$ m/min. During this time, it is not difficult to calculate the length of the thread pulled from the surface of the cocoon by the following equation

$$L = V \cdot t \quad (7)$$

Here, V is the speed of the mechanism that collects the loess washed off the surface of the cocoon, minute-1;

T is the time, in minutes, that the continuous end of the cocoon thread is under the mechanism of shaking the cocoons.

As can be seen from the equation, the length of the thread pulled from the surface of the cocoon is not 280 mm, but 14400-20000 mm.

When the length of the threads in string-shaped cocoons was studied, it was found that this type of waste has different lengths not only in the form of ropes, but also in the form of elementary fibers. It is more appropriate to group this type of fibrous waste into the category of long fiber waste. Therefore, in order to obtain silk spun from this type of waste, it is necessary to staple them.

The waste cut from the cocoons of the cocoons is a relatively uniform cocoon in terms of fiber length, which is steamed and wrapped around the surface of the cocoons before being sent to the cocoons supplier where the continuous ends of the cocoons are found and cut at

the end of each work shift according to their technological dimensions, the length of the cocoons in the cut silk waste is set depends on the diameter of the cocoon and the thickness of the cocoon threads wrapped around the surface of the cocoon.

When examining the length of fiber waste cut from the cocoons of the SKE-4-VU machine with $d = 22$ mm, it was found that the length of the fibers obeys the normal distribution law and the arithmetic mean length of the threads is 61.3 mm [18;18 19-p].

FEIYU 2000 EX cocooning machine has a diameter of 11 mm. Due to the small diameter of the cocoon, it is difficult to cut the cocoons on its surface, the cocoons are pulled from the cocoons, resulting in a tightly coiled rope-like form of silk waste, which is difficult to separate into individual fibers. From this it can be concluded that the silk waste cut from the cocoons belongs to the short fiber category for spinning silk.

The innermost part formed when the cocoon is spun is called the core, and from this type of fiber waste, the first, second and third layers are obtained.

Natural silk mainly consists of fibroin, sericin and a small amount of various organic compounds - oil, waxy substance, dye and mineral salts, in general, natural silk consists of 70-80% of fibroin, 20-30% of sericin, 1.6-3.9% of various consists of chemicals and 1.1-1.7% mineral substances. Since fibroin consists of 48-49% carbon, 6.1-6.4% oxygen, 17.4-18.9% nitrogen, it is considered a high-molecular protein. Its elementary formula is as follows - $(S_{13}N_{23}N_5ob)_n$.

It was proved by Japanese authors that the amino acid content of fibroin crystal (insoluble) and amorphous (soluble) sections is not very different [19;119-p].

It should be noted separately that the amount of fibroin in silk does not depend on the breed and hybrids of the mulberry silkworm, but its molecular weight varies widely (from 3 to 40).

After studying the chemical composition of natural silk as cocoon shell, raw silk and fibrous waste, a surfactant and a water-soluble drug were synthesized from their non-industrial waste.

As the object of our research, water-soluble polymers P-1, P-2, ShK, PSRK, MS-1, MS-2, synthesized by alkaline hydrolysis, are industrial wastes of silk - fluffy cocoon slime, 3-grass bed, shell of invalid cocoons, SVAN, KO-1, sulfocarboxylate and other solvents and distilled water were obtained.

The methods of Ph.D., Professor L.Yu. Yunusov and Associate Professor G.S. Usmanov were used to synthesize a water-soluble drug used in cocoon storage, cocooning, and preliminary processing of silk fiber waste. The water-soluble drug to be synthesized was obtained under the conditions of production (see Figure 3) in the indicated equipment.

Figure 3. Water-soluble drug synthesis device

1-reactor for hydrolyzate preparation; 2-disc filter; 3rd silencer; 4-hydrolyzate neutralization reactor; 5-a container in which ore (acid) is placed; 6-reservoir, 7-dryer.

Reactor (1) is used to prepare the hydrolyzate solution, where 2.0% sodium alkali and trisodium phosphate are prepared. For this, 170-180 l of softened water is poured through the faucet. 5 kg of tableted sodium alkali and 5 kg of trisodium phosphate are taken, mixed with a mechanical device, and a 2.0% alkali solution is added to it, and 7.5 kg of non-industrial silk waste, containing up to 30% crushed cotton, is added. Then, closing the lid of the reactor, steam at a temperature of 96-1000 C is supplied to it and it is heated until it boils. The ventilation system is also activated.

After the substances in the reactor are boiled together and the silk fiber waste is completely dissolved, the boiling is continued for 2 hours with constant stirring. The prepared hydrolyzate solution is cooled and 0.5-1.0 atm. is passed through a disk filter using compressed air. The purified solution is poured into the clarifier (3) and its volume is determined. The prepared hydrolyzate is neutralized with sulfate or phosphate ore (acid) in the reactor (4) in a ratio of 1x5 - 1x10. For this, the required amount of hydrolyzate is poured from the clarifier (3), and acid is poured from the ore (acidic) container (5). This is added until the pH of the mixture is 7.0. Drying of the finished preparation is carried out in the drying device (7). The process is monitored using the pH meter "pH-340" or indicator paper that detects water or aqueous solution to 1.0-12.0. "rN-meter" type equipment and EV-74 type ionomer were used in our experiments. The water-soluble drug neutralized with sulfuric acid was provisionally named PS00-1. In the second version of the experiment, the hydrolyzate was neutralized with phosphorus ore and tentatively named PS00-2.

A small amount of sulfuric acid solution is added to the technological water used in the production process of the silk industry. Since the basis of this solution is ore, it has a great negative effect on the metal part of the looms of carding, sericulture and waste preliminary processing, as well as on the health of the workers of the looms. Therefore, in order to eliminate the mentioned shortcomings, the preparation described above was synthesized.

It was noted above that the initial raw materials used for the synthesis of the water-soluble drug contain up to 30-40% crushed sponge. Also, in the process of hydrolysis, fibroin, sericin, oil absorbed into the ground sponge silk waste, a number of amino acid fractions are separated into residues and oil ores. In addition, the newly synthesized water-soluble drug became universal compared to solvents such as soap-soda or MS-1, MS-2, MS-3, as it contained RO₄-3 ions instead of SO₄-2 and Cl ions.

In confirmation of this, PS00-1 and PS00-2 water-soluble drug showed that it can be used for 3-4 days both in cocoon storage and cocoon washing, as a means of softening glued areas in raw silk re-wrapping, and in silk waste deglutization and degreasing processes, but it cannot be stored for a long time, it cannot be transported from one side to the other, because it starts to rot. Therefore, it is advisable to use the drug as a dry powder. For this, it is necessary to increase the amount of the component of the drug and dry it.

An alternative concentration for the preparation of the drug is as follows: sodium alkali 4%, trisodium phosphate 2%, third herb bed 5.4%. Required softened water 170 l, or sodium alkali 5 kg, trisodium phosphate 5 kg, silk waste 7.5 kg.

The remaining technical dimensions do not change. The neutralized drug solution in the reservoir (6) is poured into the drying tank and the drug is obtained as a powder. It is advisable to store the drug in polyethylene bags in a dry, cool place. The storage period is 1 year.

The results of any research are evaluated by one or another quality indicator of the studied object. In particular, the synthesized water-soluble drug is determined by various experiments.

DISCUSSIONS.

Cocoons are stored in warehouses of the cocoons to ensure continuous operation of the cocoons. Although this may seem simple, it is very important for technological processes. Also, creation of methods to eliminate defects by developing methods to preserve the properties of silk fiber waste, improve physical and mechanical properties, quality indicators, shorten the technological system of the initial processing of waste and eliminate problems arising in this regard, use of electroactive water surfactants by methods of increasing the efficiency of the process of obtaining high-quality fiber by processing silk waste at an optimal concentration with L.Yu. widely covered in his works.

In the industrial cocoons grown in China and India, the percentage of cocoons that are not suitable for spinning is 3-5%, the yield of raw silk is 42-44%, most of the cocoons are 95-98% of average size, and the quality of raw silk is ensured based on these indicators [20]. Taking into account that in our republic, the percentage of cocoons that are not suitable for spinning is 25-30%, and the amount of raw silk from cocoons is 26-29%, experiments on the use of silk fiber waste in similar industrial enterprises were studied.

CONCLUSIONS.

As a result of the conducted research, it was possible to conclude as follows that the amount of silk fiber waste and the products obtained from them were fully analyzed during the technological processes of cocoon cultivation, raw silk, cooked silk and silk bobbin threads, and production of silk products;

Some physical and mechanical properties and characteristics of silk fiber waste generated during the technological processes of preparation of cocoons for spinning, spinning and analysis of quality indicators of obtained raw silk in cocooning enterprises were studied and analyzed;

The amount of residual sericin and oil in the fiber waste of silk produced during spinning and spinning technological processes was analyzed and studied;

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